

DARK AND SARDONIC HUMOUR: A STUDY OF KIRAN NAGARKAR'S *RAVAN & EDDIE*

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Humour is not resigned; it is rebellious. It signifies not only the triumph of the ego but also of the pleasure principle... Sigmund Freud

Abstract:

On a grand scale, dark humour is estimated to constitute disruptive values and systems, a defensive strategy and a satirical element containing taboo materials as subjects. Few critics like Mathew Winston and Brom Weber opined that the term black/dark humour has been imported from France "L humor noir" which in English translation becomes black humour. It functioned as a central doctrine of French surrealism almost from its inception in the 1920's. In 1939 Andre Breton, the French surrealist writer coined the term Black humour and defined it as "superior revolt of the mind" (Breton xvi). Black humour is nothing more than laughing at a tragically insensitive environment. Black humour exposes the absurdity/ridiculousness of value systems, human life and insanities by juxtaposing the melancholic elements with comical ones as is portrayed deftly in Kiran Nagarkar's maiden English novel *Ravan and Eddie*. The novelist depicts the parallel lives of two boys Ravan and Eddie in a very amusing, hilarious, and satirical style by intertwining the religious-cultural inconsistencies and clashes of the two communities - Hinduism and Christianity. The present study intends to explore how the author exploits dark humour in depicting the harsh reality of Sardonic society, as well as the tensions, coldness, antagonism connection, and rivalry between two religions, Hinduism and Christianity.

Keywords: Dark humour, religious discrimination, water wars, caste, gender, hopelessness, helplessness, modern man's predicament and Chawl life.

Introduction:

On a larger scale, dark humour is said to represent disruptive beliefs and systems, a defence tactic, and a sarcastic aspect with taboo issues. This style is used effectively in Kiran Nagarkar's works, which blend tragic and funny situations. Nagarkar's works deal with typical dark comedy subjects such as violence (murder, domestic violence, torture), sexuality (sodomy, homosexuality, incest, infidelity), discrimination (chauvinism, racism, sexism), disease (depression, disability, suicide, terminal illness, insanity), and religion. The present study examines Kiran Nagarkar's debut English novel *Ravan & Eddie* through the lens of dark humour. The novelist depicts the parallel lives of two boys in a very amusing, hilarious, and satirical style by intertwining the religious-cultural inconsistencies and clashes of the two communities - Hinduism and Christianity in a post-colonial context. He calls the sacredness of religion and communalism into question through comedy and violence. Nagarkar's iconoclastic and irreverent style frequently reflects the numerous contradictions that define modern India which celebrates its fractured and fragmented identity.

Nagarkar, an Indian author, playwright, and screenwriter who writes in both Marathi and English has made a name for himself in India and around the world. He has been appropriately described as a cosmopolitan, experimenter, visionary, humanist, genius, and great scholar. According to German literary critic Denis Scheck, Kiran Nagarkar is one of the truly outstanding new discoveries of the last few years.

His debut Marathi novel, *Saat Sakkam Trechalis* (1974), later translated into English as *Seven Sixes are Forty-Three* (1980), is recognized as a major achievement in Marathi literature. *Ravan & Eddie* (1995), his second novel, was a literary bestseller. *Cuckold* (1997), his third novel about mystic Meerabai's husband, Bhoj Raj, received the Sahitya Akademi Award in 2001. *God's Little Soldier*, a

narrative about a liberal Muslim boy's experience with religious orthodoxy was released in 2006. *The Extras*, a sequel to *Ravan & Eddie* that follows Ravan and Eddie's adult lives as extras in Bollywood was released in 2012. *Ravan & Eddie*'s final sequel, *Rest in Peace*, was published in 2015.

Nagarkar is a talented storyteller who employs new storytelling tactics that captivate the reader. According to Khushwant Singh, an Indian author, Kiran Nagarkar is a natural storyteller with an impeccable eye for detail and an erotic artist. His writing approach alternates between ongoing storylines and documentary segments. His writing style is informal with colourful metaphors and sensual language that address a wide range of topics. He employs different narrative approaches like the digression method which is used in classical writings like the *Ramayana*. In addition, he incorporates epistolary, authorial memories and character-sung melodies into his storytelling.

Nagarkar was born in Mumbai in 1942 to a Brahmin family named Chitpavan. He had primary education in both Marathi and English. He received his postgraduate degree in English literature from Mumbai's South Indian Education Society (SIES) College. He is well-known for his works' sharp-edged black humour, wit, and irony which are used in a variety of shades, tones, and textures. His works explore current multi-cultural societies, superstition, politics, history, myth, ethical and sociocultural dilemmas, the Bollywood world and religious obsessive faith. According to Gaikwad (2015), Nagarkar "used humour to correct, to restore, to define, to cope with situations, to mirror truths, and to set a value on things in Indian English literature. He is known for his use of dark and passionate humour in his novels" ("Kiran" 65).

Nagarkar uses comedy as a survival strategy as well as a tool for understanding and empathizing with human situations. He portrays his protagonists as rebellious, courageous, and optimistic. Nagarkar's writings depict dystopic and disturbing pictures using raunchy, ribald, and witty humour. Nagarkar's writings are a sharp critique of present societal realities such as religious, linguistic, economic, and social issues, giving voice to the underprivileged and oppressed parts of Indian society. As Hasan (2012) remarks:

Nagarkar is a genuine experimentalist: he combines in his writing a tremendous instinct for story telling with a rare openness of imagination. He is willing to go where it takes him, express it in whatever form and through whichever language. What remains constant is his subversive pleasure in fiction for its own sake. It makes him one of our most precious writers. (84)

Nagarkar's first English novel, *Ravan & Eddie*, depicts the multifaceted evolution of the two main characters, Ravan, a Maratha Hindu, and Eddie, a Roman Catholic Christian, in their respective socio-cultural contexts. Jarandikar (2011) observes that "in a typical postmodernist way, Nagarkar deconstructs the homogenous and harmonious Indian world through the novel *Ravan & Eddie*" ("De-glorification" 2). It's a humorous story set in Mumbai's Byculla in the 1950s and 1960s, in Central Works Department Chawl number 17 for the lower working class.

The story opens with Ram falling down from the fourth-floor balcony off his mother Parvatibai's arms. Eddie's father, Victor Coutinho, an airplane technician, catches Ram but dies on the scene from shock. Violet, Victor's wife, witnesses the collision and points her finger at Ram, exclaiming, "Murderer, murderer" (*Ravan & Eddie* 6). Ram is now known as the "Cain Murderer" among the inhabitants of CWD chawl (*R&E* 10).

While the Catholic community mourns Victor's tragic death and prepares for his funeral rites, Parvatibai invites a Brahmin priest to perform Satyanarayana puja as an expression of gratitude to the Almighty for her son's miraculous escape. The solemnity of a Christian funeral procession contrasts with the meaningless rites of Satyanarayan Pooja. While death is mourned in somber songs, survival is celebrated loudly in the furious recitation of Vedic hymns. The author earns a brownie point in the novel's opening scene by playing the mysterious ways of God in the life and death game. The saver dies, and the survivor takes on the legendary villain's name, 'Ravan'.

The author was successful in depicting the stark contrasts of life in his portrayal of Catholic funeral rites. The hearse is attractively decked like a new bride's bed, and the Hindus of the chawl are in awe of the ritual, wondering "even if you were born a Hindu, it was worthwhile dying a Catholic" (*R&E* 8). The author's expert use of black/dark humour reaches its zenith when the solemn funeral

cortege “doubled as a maternity ward” (*R&E* 14), where Violet gives birth to Eddie. Dr. Pravin Waghmare (2019) rightly contends:

Nagarkar’s dominant stylistic devices are black humour and corrosive irony. He gives humorous treatment to the shocking, horrific and macabre elements. His characters caught in a whirlpool of indifferent and insensitive cross-cultural milieu display a marked disillusionment and cynicism. They are without comfort and with little hope. If they can’t do anything about it, they prefer to laugh and bear the burden of life. His wit is mordant and humour sardonic. This flippant attitude to look at the world of sorrows and sufferings he has created is his forte. (82)

Parvati renames her son Ravan to protect him from the evil eye. The naming of Ravan is a great mockery, because Ram is considered an ideal of virtues in Indian mythology, whereas Ravan is considered his opposite. Modern Ravan is required to ‘hang the Albatross’ around his neck, the sin for which he bears no responsibility, and ponders over its redemption. Nagarkar depicts the modern identity of Ravan, who is in other ways associated with wicked forces in the epic *Ramayana*.

The Pawar family, which includes Shankar, Parvati, and Ram, lives on the fourth floor of the chawl while the Coutinho family, including Victor, Violet, and Peita, lives on the fifth floor. Their families are not on good terms for years and are hostile to one another. The two boys, who are completely different from one another, have bittersweet, parallel lives that frequently cause problems despite remaining innocent throughout the book.

Nagarkar exploits the theme chauvinism through RSS (Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh) Sabha, a volunteer organization of Hindu revivalists, its events and the fanaticism of its members. The Sabha hopes to rekindle the “fires of Hinduism” by reversing the tide of “lost souls” who have converted to other religions and bringing them back into the Hindu fold (*R&E* 20). Ironically, Ravan, a born Hindu, was rejected by the Sabha, drawing a similarity to Nathuram Godse, Mahatma Gandhi’s killer. Eddie, on the other hand, was greeted with great irony, utilizing the biblical story of the “prodigal son,” whose forefathers converted to Christianity decades ago and was now returning “amongst his own” (*R&E* 33). According to Dr. Nitin Jarandikar, Kiran Nagarkar’s novel *Ravan & Eddie* employs mythical realms from two religious cultures to depict the complex predicament of modern man living in a multicultural society.

The RSS Sabha episode is a tremendous farce because a born Hindu was denied and a born Christian was welcomed. Ironically, a born Christian is regarded as the hope and future leader of the RSS Sabha. Appa Achrekar compliments Eddie, saying, “Eddie Coutinho, mark my words, for my prophecies have always come true, will be one of the great leaders of the Sabha. Our tradition and our future are safe in the hands of the people like Eddie Coutinho” (*R&E* 128). Eddie outperforms everyone else and becomes Guruji’s favourite student.

The book extensively satirizes and mocks Lele Guruji’s behaviour of promoting religious conversion from Christianity to Hinduism, including presenting numerous allures to young minds. Eddie receives a book titled *Stories from the Mahabharata and Shri Krishna’s Life*, as well as a Wilson pen, for his great performance in the Sabha. Eddie’s mother, who believes Eddie has betrayed Jesus Christ, drags him to Father D’Souza for punishment. She accuses him of committing “a heinous sin” (*R&E* 131) of reading and listening to those stories against the Christian religious ethos, and requests to “exorcize him” (*R&E* 130). Father D’Souza threatens Eddie with excommunication if he worships anyone other than “our Lord God Jesus Christ” (*R&E* 132), asserting that the Bible is God’s eternal message. Eddie refuses to accept a religion granted by birth that cannot tolerate various identities, therefore he says that the Gita is likewise regarded as God’s word, and that reading the Gita was akin to reading the Bible because both were texts with stories. Nagarkar’s use of dark humour in mocking religious texts is highly commendable when he claims that both were texts with stories.

Eddie realizes that, while Jesus is still his Lord, he cannot bring himself to worship a “goody-goody” and “glum and long-faced” deity whose flesh had to be eaten and whose blood had to be spilt every time one communicated with him in the Eucharist (*R&E* 113). Instead, he is captivated to the Hindu god Krishna because of his mischievous nature, which includes stealing yogurt and wooing Radha. In response to Father D’Souza’s representation of Christian expectations, Eddie allows Father

D'Souza to battle for his soul rather than himself. It's interesting to see Fr. D'Souza get caught up in confessionals. He is not sure if Eddie is playing his "usual tricks" or if "God had smitten the child and his grief was real" (*R&E* 255). Eddie's physical and spiritual body became a war between Hindu and Catholic clergymen. Nagarkar's tongue-in-cheek attitude toward constructing the religious preferences of the two characters is an excellent example of his use of dark humour.

Nagarkar presents religious institutions with no authority, implying that they have lost their sanctity and will no longer be a binding morality for individuals in the postmodern society. Jarandikar rightly notes that "On one side, Nagarkar has depicted the parental authority as powerless, on the other side, the religious institution is also projected as hollow and without any authority" ("Motif" 7). The episode of Eddie's confession is a big mockery of void ritual. To purge his soul from the sin, Eddie's Grana asks him to go "for confession" (*R&E* 250), and the desperate Eddie invents outrage after outrage to satisfy the priest's curiosity, from ordering plates of mutton samosa at the Light of Iran and leaving without paying to going to the Railway Colony in Byculla to look up through the slats in the wooden staircase at the underwear of Anglo-Indian girls.

Eddie's clothes are damaged when collecting a ticket for the movie *Rock Around the Clock*, but in the confession box, he tells Father D'Souza false claims about the Mawali Gang's attack on Ravan. Eddie, ironically, names his imagined gang 'Do or Die Devils.' Despite the presence of religious institutions, the heroes are unable to escape destruction and violence. Eddie's efforts had paid off, as Father D'Souza eventually erupts with "Verily, Eddie, you have sinned" (*R&E* 254). Eddie admits, "I was wrong, Father Agnello, I've sinned most terribly. As God is my witness, I'll never again do what I did in the past. Punish me, Father, punish me any way you want" (*R&E* 255). The falsity of 'confession' is exposed satirically with deft touch of dark humour when Eddie lies to the priest.

Nagarkar attempts to demonstrate that mere confession would not result in redemption because 'confession' itself has become a mere ritual with no sanctity. When confronted with the realities of a wicked, irrational world, socially constructed categories such as religion and the values that underpin them, which stem from ideals of order and the belief in rational development for the future, cease to be feasible. Father Agnello proclaims Eddie's "unorthodox repentance" for a crime he did not commit (*R&E* 255). A dark mocking critique of the Christian ways of sin, repentance and redemption is presented by the author.

Both Christianity and Hinduism are portrayed as having both rejuvenating and debilitating demands, as evidenced by the imagery of Christ's blood needing to be spilt every time the Eucharist is celebrated, and Hinduism becoming "an ocean of blood," with "a hole at the bottom, so you had to keep filling it" (*R&E* 19). Nagarkar, like Christianity, distinguishes himself from Hinduism by attacking the Hindu concepts of 'sin' and 'salvation' through the narrative of Abhimanyu, who dies without having committed any sin. Indeed, he believes that all religions are equally corrupt. Nagarkar's most scathing criticism is intended at religion and its role in emphasizing class, religious, and cultural distinctions among chawl inhabitants. Sprigge (1973), an English novelist and biographer, argues that religion was "man's most extraordinary aberration and an irresistible invitation to mockery" (40).

Religious belief does not give protection from the effects of a poorly structured society but rather reinforces them, and Nagarkar proves that knowledge and a wry sense of humour are better defences against life's tragedies. Religion, like other social organizations that promote arbitrary privilege has degraded into institutionalized oppression, and Nagarkar regards it as a legitimate target. He makes no recommendations for a different way to organize the world. By juxtaposing Hindu and Christian mythology, Nagarkar emphasizes the modern man's tragic entrapment in the world of 'sin' and 'guilt', with no chance of 'redemption'. As Kamalakar B Gaikwad (2015) points out, "Nagarkar projects the complexity of modern man living in a mixed society with mixed identity and multicultural milieu. He reveals the intricacies of dual identity of the character in modern times" ("A Critical" 2).

Ravan becomes well-known among his peers for murdering both Mahatma Gandhi and Victor Coutinho, and this blot on his life remains. Ravan spends his time debating Eddie and his mother's murder accusations. He is baffled as to how and when Eddie's father was killed. Throughout the narrative, Ravan bears the burden of 'murder' despite his inability to remember anything about it. He attempts to "ask for proof all his life, but the only proof that mattered he had already heard" in the

epithets screamed at him by others (*R&E* 35). Ironically, after learning about Ravan's past, many individuals sought him out, requesting him to execute the most heinous acts and paying him cash in advance, rather than spitting on him and fleeing from his mere shadow. Towards the end of the novel, Ravan's condition worsens when his own friend Shobhan Sarang commits suicide, and everyone begins to suspect Ravan. His grave situation of acquiring fame as a murderer and his confusion over it is satirized with a tint of dark humour.

Ravan enrolls in Mr. Billimoria's academy and begins learning the martial art 'tae kwon do'. Throughout the years, he has won various 'tae kwon do' competitions. Mr. Billimoria is gentle, while Lele Guruji is stern. Parallel to Eddie's entry into the Sabha, Ravan encounters St. Theresa's Catholic school. While Eddie is lured to Malkhamb, Ravan is drawn to Tae Kwon Do classes.

The author seizes the opportunity to highlight the hard economic realities of chawl living in the digression "A Harangue on Poverty" (*R&E* 38). The novelist says "In India, as in other poor countries, we have a line that is invisible and abstract and yet more powerful and pervasive than anything the West or the Japanese have invented. It is called the poverty line" (*R&E* 38-9). Above the poverty line, there are three meals per day; below it, there are 2.99 to 0 meals.

As a result of the excessive number of people, the central corridor on each floor of the chawl is utilized for various purposes.

In the afternoons the women cleaned the rice or wheat, combed their daughters' hair or left the papads to dry on a thin piece of cloth; some evenings you'd see a game of cricket in progress here; this was the venue for the annual carrom tournaments and at nights the corridor became a dormitory for many of the children and adults from the floor. (*R&E* 66-7)

The black humourists like Nagarkar feel that the most rational approach to confronting the distressing truth and irrationality of life is to laugh it out as Kamalakar B Gaikwad (2016) notes, Nagarkar "employs the humour as a measure of emotional disengagement" ("The Current Perspective" 64).

The author provides a humorous account of the harsh realities of the urban subclass that lives below the poverty line. The novel's characters are constantly plagued by illness, badly cared for children, and unsanitary living conditions. Instead of mourning these pitiful problems such as poverty, water warfare, untouchability, religious, caste, and gender biases, Nagarkar presents them in a humorous manner, encouraging the reader to cope with the pathetic scenario. According to Kamalakar B Gaikwad (2016), Nagarkar "employs humour as a measure of emotional disengagement" ("The Current Perspective" 64). The true problems of chawl people's lives are shown as they are because black humourists are concerned with what is, not what should be. Bruce (1992), an American comedian, stated in his performances that "what should be...measure up to that dirty lie" (123).

The author depicts the true state of poverty through the female characters Parvatibai and Violet. There are many similarities between Ravan and Eddie's mothers. Ravan and Eddie both come from a fatherless society where patriarchy remains powerful and well-served. Parvati, Ravan's mother, provides food for migrant mill factory workers by working "twelve hours a day in front of three monster kerosene stoves, cooking lunch and dinner for fifty bachelors, or at least quasi-bachelors" (*R&E* 40). Violet, a widow, works hard for her family through stitching clothes till late night. They live below the poverty line in a thinly partitioned single room where even whispered murmurs can be heard as clearly as on the amplifier. The novel's comedy darkens when the author recounts the condition of the female characters in a caustic tone.

The next digression, "The Great Water Wars" (*R&E* 67), intensifies the Chawl inhabitants' hunt for basic necessities such as water. Water, which is considered one of life's necessities is not readily available for consumption by chawl people. They have to strive to get it since there is more demand than supply. When there is no running water, this frequently leads to battles over it. The author characterizes water as "more powerful than the Almighty" (*R&E* 69), and "on any given day, there were anywhere between a hundred to two hundred and fifty pots waiting in queue. What a sight it was" (*R&E* 70) together with "the response to the sight of flowing water is desperation, a frenzy of pointless activity and loss of sanity" (*R&E* 71). Everyone observed the need of water and said, "Water, Blood. Is there a difference? The water wars had started" (*R&E* 72). The author's harsh sarcasm reaches a

climax when he states, "they should have killed for water, the men and women of the CWD chawls. People have been known to kill for less: religion; language; the flag; the colour of a person's skin or his caste; breaking the queue at a petrol pump" (*R&E* 67). Nagarkar's use of dark humour in his realistic depictions of the water issue is commendable.

The humour of a dark sort is observed when the author mocks Indian Gods saying "rains are an act of God in India... That is the essence of God: He gives with two hands and takes away with eight more. Why else would Indian gods and goddesses have several pairs of hands?" (*R&E* 68). Black humour seems to have little respect for the religious values, Gods, Goddesses and as Weber (1983) states "Black humour violates sacred and secular taboos alike without restraint or compunction" (362).

In the following digression, titled "A Short Digression on Snow" (*R&E* 81), the author mocks the stress placed on fairness between men and women. Chawl women use Afghan snow to look fair and attractive, as fairness is valued more highly than riches and power. Tara represents the picture of the colonial stereotype. It is the legacy of a society that insists on designating its women as 'fairer sex.'

To be a fair is to be God's chosen. Fairness was more precious than immortality, nirvana, or moksha. It was on a par with virginity. It was more desirable than all the treasures of the Mogul emperors and the inspiration of the poets. Admittedly, not more sought after than wealth and power, but just as potent and indispensable. For truly what are wealth and power without a fair skin? (*R&E* 81-2)

The author highlights the connection between fairness and prior life karma, stating that individuals who "walk the righteous path in their previous life are born fair ... To be dark was to have committed original sin" (*R&E* 82). The author is adept in making caustic remarks about fairness.

The novelist provides an unsettling depiction of caste and gender-related violence, presenting the problem of marriage in an Indian family, using the example of Mr. Sarang's family, with nine unmarried daughters. He explores themes such as domestic violence, abuse, disability, and suicide. Mr. Sarang, who belongs to the high caste but has a meagre salary, resorts to hitting his wife and daughters for various reasons. His violent behaviour appears to be the result of his growing frustration, concealed beneath the anxiety of finding grooms and arranging money to marry off his daughters.

Tara, one of the nine daughters, who is in love with a lower caste untouchable named Shahaji Kadam, gets caught going to the movies with him. Tara's father, Mr. Sarang, reacts strongly to her defiant attitude, scolding her, "she's lying. The bitch is always lying" (*R&E* 108). Shobhan, one of his daughters, is intelligent and athletic, but she has club feet, which her father mocks. She begs him not to react because it is her birthday. Mr. Sarang responds, "the izzat of our family is at stake and you talk of your bloody birthday, you cloven-hoofed goat. Do you know who she has been seeing on the sly?" (*R&E* 109). Mr. Sarang, frightened, asks, "what happens to my other daughters? Who will marry them once they discover that we have a Mahar, an untouchable, sorry, a neo-Buddhist, isn't that what one calls them now, among us?" (*R&E* 110).

Mr. Sarang does not want his daughter marrying "the untouchable slime from the ground floor" (*R&E* 109). When Ravan first sees Tara Sarang and Shahaji Kadam together, he thinks for the first time of a race that is neither Hindu nor Catholic, but rather a 'minority' that is considered as an outcast by both societies. He questions who, what, and why Shahaji and his people are untouchables.

Tara, unable to endure her father's harsh and violent behaviour, eventually finds her voice: "we are all going to die spinsters, Father, because there are just too many of us and you haven't got the money to bribe a caste-Hindu to take us off your hands" (*R&E* 110). As a result, Mr. Sarang kicks Tara in the stomach and declares, "no daughter of mine is going to live with an untouchable: Never. He kicked her again, a little harder, if that was possible. When Shobhan tried to pull him away, he threw her against the wall. A slow, red pool was forming under Tara" (*R&E* 110). According to Nabar (1995), women in India face three types of discrimination "sex-based (*stri-jati*), caste-based (*jati*), and class-based. To be caste as woman in India is to live out this triple-layered existence" (50). The author champions in jeering at the customs and societal concerns such as the dowry system.

The spread of Christianity in India appears to be a reaction against Hinduism's evil practices such as caste servitude and discrimination. The author satirically reveals the roots of the emergence of Catholicism.

It did not cross the minds of most Hindus that barring exceptions, they were responsible for Catholicism in India. The outcastes of Hinduism, the untouchables, who fell beyond the pale of the caste system, had ample reason to convert to Catholicism. The caste-Hindus, as a matter of fact, left them no choice. As sub-humans they were little better than slaves. (R&E 175)

The converted Indian Christian Catholics had a sense of self-worth and dignity, and they were given “a chance to work at any profession they fancied” (R&E 175), which was not permitted in the Hindu system. Even in the chawls, a hierarchy exists, with Catholics living on the fifth level, Hindus on the other floors, and untouchables and lower caste Hindus on the lowest floors.

Hindus revere them as those people, believing that even their shadows can taint them. Neither Hindus nor Christians would approach these outcasts. The unfortunate reality is that women are at the bottom of this system. According to Shirodkar (1996), their position is “worse than that of the untouchables because while the former are at least left to live “their own lives” within the confines of “their own society”, the women are dictated to by the men folk” (225). Polhemus (1982), an author and professor, correctly observes that “the patterns of human inequality may develop naturally in individual minds; but inequalities of class, sex, and wealth, institutionalized and perpetuated by leeching selfishness, must be shown up for the terrible practical jokes that they are” (216). The author presents the problem of caste and gender discrimination in an artistic manner, laced with scornful humour.

The author believes that it was “religion that was the source of all the differences between the two communities” (R&E 172). Hindus attend free municipal schools, whilst Catholics attend priest-and nun-run schools. Hindus “bathe in the morning, Goan Catholics in the evening” (R&E 171). Hindus also shower their established gods. However, Goan Catholics “didn’t think that salvation and bathing were casually related” (R&E 172). Hindus visit temples whenever they feel like it, but Catholics attend church every Sunday. Hindus speak Marathi, whereas Catholics speak both English and Konkani. India is never homogeneous, either culturally or spiritually. India has a long history of religious tolerance, towards different religions like Islam, Christianity, Buddhism, Jainism, and Hinduism. According to sociologist T. K. Oommen, converting to Hinduism raises the question of whose caste the new convert should be ascribed. Hinduism is considered a non-proselytizing religion due to the inextricable link between caste and religion.

A tinge of dark humour is observed in Nagarkar’s portrayal of Hindus’ filthy habits: “Hindus didn’t think that spitting was peeing through the mouth” (R&E 172). Catholics do not eat paan and cannot be held accountable for such obscene public behaviour. The narrator builds reductive associations of Catholics as un-Indian, which is reflected in lines like “Goan Catholics were born and bred in India but their umbilical cord stretched all the way to Lisbon” (R&E 16), and Eddie’s name “felt, tasted, smelt, and sounded alien” (R&E 25). Nagarkar’s statements demonstrate religious indifference, as he sarcastically criticizes on Catholicism and Hinduism, as well as their respective eccentricities.

In his view of the divided world, Nagarkar questions through Eddie how Christians can be discriminated against Hindus because there is no difference between them as humans. Whatever religion one follows, a human being is still a human being, religion cannot be used to discriminate against people because every religion consists of different types of people. The author not only depicts religious distinctions by portraying the communities’ lifestyles, traditions, and living patterns in a darkly humorous tone, but he also emphasizes the ridiculousness of these inequalities in the plot.

In the same digression, Nagarkar includes a brief discussion of language in which he peppers the text with the hidden truth of urban India, namely the power of knowing English. According to him, the world is divided into two groups of people: “Those who have English are the haves, and those who don’t, are the have-nots” (R&E 177). With deft touch of black humour, the author highlights the value of English by asserting, “English is a mantra, a maha-mantra. It is an ‘open sesame’ that doesn’t open mere doors, it opens up new worlds and allows you to cross over from one universe to another” (R&E 177). In the mockery of Hindus’ inability to use English, the humour of a dark sort is observed when Nagarkar says “English was the thorn in the side of the Hindus ... It was the great leveller. It gave caste-Hindus a taste of their own medicine. It made them feel like untouchables. It also turned the

tables. The former outcasts could now look down upon their Hindu neighbours" (R&E 176). About embracing other religions, the author says in a darkly satirical style, "Dr. Ambedkar was wrong to convert millions of his untouchable brethren to Buddhism. He should have converted them to English" (R&E 176).

The novelist observes that "Vivekanand met Ramakrishna Paramhansa, Mephistopheles found Faust, the Buddha sat under a pipal tree and gained enlightenment, the Virgin Mary woke from a deep sleep with an immaculate conception, Ravan saw *Dil Deke Dekho*" (R&E 178). Ravan pays for the movie by selling "his books one after another" (R&E 186), as well as his mother's gold jewellery. The author's skilful use of black humour reaches its zenith when Nagarkar claims Ravan "would have undone the clasp of the mangalsutra from around her neck while she slept, and pawned it" (R&E 186-7). Fortunately, *Dil Deke Dekho* was removed after celebrating a silver jubilee, and Parvatibai's mangalsutra remained around her neck.

On the other hand, Eddie, Ravan's equivalent, exhibits the same behavioural tendency. He deceives his mother, uses grocer's money, and tells a potential suitor lies about his mother, steals from the charity box, sells movie tickets on the black market, and watches the English film *Rock Around the Clock* fifteen times despite the fact that the Church has not approved it because it encourages rowdy behaviour among teenagers. When Eddie's mother and Father D'Souza learned that he had seen the film *Rock Around the Clock*, they were shocked since they consider it an evil in and of itself, promoting profanity and sensuality, whereas Eddie considers it a fairly ordinary thing. The narrative focuses on two guys whose lives share identical occurrences, from joining in activities to becoming addicted to a specific sort of entertainment and eventually sliding into bad habits.

Ravan becomes a thief, while Eddie becomes a liar and does whatever they want. Ravan and Eddie are not twins, nor are they stepbrothers, but their lives are parallel. They were separated by one city, one chawl, two storeys, two cultures, two languages, two religions, two women's enmity and "how could their paths possibly meet?" (R&E 190). As Geeta Doctor (1995) points out, Ravan and Eddie are the "two halves of Nagarkar's expertly choreographed study of cause and effect, image and illusion, brotherhood and betrayal, Hindu/Christian, a variation perhaps, but a valid one nonetheless on the deeply divided Indian psyche, have been set into motion. Almost instantly, the caricature element darkens" ("Bom Bom Bombai Meri Hai" 27).

The novel's humour darkens further when the dark side of Bombay's lust and sexuality is presented, and taboo topics are introduced into the narration. Eddie sees a naked picture of lady Anita Ekberg in sex magazine *Playboy* and sings, "Little boy, little boy, what are you holding in your hand? Is it a bat and ball, or your cock standing tall?" (R&E 306). When his gaze is fixed on Father Agnello's, he shreds the picture and flushes it. Nagarkar presents a mocking depiction of two boys' school life, their mischievous actions, their changing minds, and strange conduct, but maintains their innocence even though they cheat and lie on face. Niti Sampat Patel (2003) correctly observes that "the novel's riotous, digressive style coincides with the bawdy, Rabelaisian adventures of Ravan and Eddie. In fact, the spirit of carnivalesque ribaldry runs right through the novel" (178).

The novel is about dedicated mothers who want their boys to have a better life than their fathers, and sons who are divided between pleasing their mothers and pursuing their own nonconformist goals. The mothers, Violet and Parvati, suffer from their sons' failings and punish them as a sort of self-torture. Despite Parvatibai's repeated instructions, Ravan solely watches movies. So, she became enraged and

whipped him across his back, caned him, and hit him with her shoes; she scratched him with her nails. She singed his calf with burning coal, almost cracked his kneecap with a rolling pin... 'Ravanya, ayyayyayyaya, just see what you've done to me. There's not a bone left in my body that's not broken and bruised. Are you listening, you wretch? Don't you have any feelings for your poor mother?' (R&E 187)

Nagarkar uses dark comedy to address topics that are deemed taboo, such as sex, and how children are subjected to sexual abuse even in a civilized society. Prakash, the protagonist's school mate, compelled Ravan to have oral sex. "Prakash grabbed hold of Ravan's hair and yanked him down... 'Open your mouth, you son of a bitch, or I'll blow your brains out'" (R&E 136-7). Prakash's

insatiable sexual desires and abrupt taming after knowing about Ravan's abilities appear ludicrous. Morris Dickstein (1997), an American scholar, correctly states that black humour is "always affronting taboos, giving offense, recalling people to their physical functions and gut reactions" (100). The author portrays sodomy and homosexuality in a harsh and scathing manner. Hasan (2012), states that "Nagarkar must be one of the few Indian writers who is able to describe sex without the sense of embarrassment that leads either to outlandish exaggeration or coy elisions" (83).

Although attacks on God, Mother, and Flag are examples of dark humour targets, Hamlin Hill, an American novelist, believes that sex humour has earned more reputation. In the depiction of illicit relationship between Shankar Rao and Lalee, Lalee calls him "mother- and sister-fucker, a whore-son, pimp, arse-buggerer, pederast, cunt-licker, father-fucker and then became highly creative in the extensions and variations of her sexual imagery" (*R&E* 210-11). The author presents incest and infidelity in a satirical manner that transcends all prudish conventions.

The hopelessness of a postmodern man is illustrated through Parvatibai with derisive humour. She feels agitated by her husband's sister Lalee, is frustrated with life, and states that "mankind was nothing but trouble" (*R&E* 233). When she sees Ananta baba, a holy man with the capacity to change destiny and fate, he blesses her with a black thread but does not say whether things would change or not. The subject of powerlessness, helplessness, and loneliness, which are reoccurring themes in the dark comedy novel, is depicted in *Ravan & Eddie* through the boys' mothers, who fail to guide their sons' lives in the right direction. In this world, man is not valued at all. His life is dictated by powers beyond his control, and he is defenceless against the forces of devastation, mutilation, and death. Nagarkar opines that 'helplessness' of modern man in this world being dejected by God is the ultimate reality.

Both Ravan and Eddie turn sixteen. Their thoughts change, and they have a more in-depth and comprehensive vision of the world. They are captivated by movies and performers and decide to work in the film industry in the sequel *The Extras*. Heroes and heroines serve as role models for younger generations. Eddie follows in the footsteps of famous rock artists, while Ravan resolves to become a nightclub singer and drummer.

Finally, the reader witnesses Ravan and Eddie's reunion, but they are quickly separated by Eddie's mother, Violet. According to Nagarkar, "parallel worlds can only meet in a geometrical Utopia called the horizon" (*R&E* 16), implying that the struggle between the two characters would never be resolved. In metaphorical terms, toward the end, Nagarkar argues, the two characters, the intersecting themes, and the myriad issues that rise above the story of the novel while emerging from its fabric, are seen in "perfect harmony, intersecting each other's orbits in a Pythagorean paradise" (*R&E* 330). The text demonstrates that, despite their variations in faiths and religious practices, their sufferings are nearly identical caused by their pressing economic problems in making ends meet, their low-cost Chawls, their routine water fights, shared bathrooms and so on.

Nagarkar triumphs in depicting the harsh reality of Sardonic society, as well as the tensions, coldness, antagonism connection, and rivalry between two religions, Hinduism and Christianity, through his use of black humour, acidic sense of irony, and laughter that almost reaches ridiculousness. The pain, fashion, ugliness, manners, morals, ideals, and struggles prevailing in the society are exhibited, so that the people become conscious of the dark realities in which they dwell unconsciously. The author, with an unerring eye, depicts the foibles of society, injustice, violence, death, and cultural chauvinism of the two communities with a grimly humorous tone. Nagarkar's humour is a dark comedy of survival, with the novel's protagonists, Ravan and Eddie, emerging as fighters rather than victims. Colletta (2003) makes the right point: "Dark humour is not the humour of change; it is the humour of survival, the humour of getting through another day with as little trauma as possible, without committing suicide or dying of loneliness" (114).

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